

Experimental

Hydroxytriazenes were prepared following the method given by Golwalkar⁴ and were identical to the authentic sample. In uv absorption studies, it was observed that in these compounds the absorption maximum appearing around 313 nm shifts to ~350 nm in alkaline medium. This observation was the basis of spectrophotometric method for determining ionisation constants following the reported methods¹⁻³. Absorbance measurements were made at Hitachi Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, using 1.00 cm matched quartz cells and Cambridge pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Procedure: A series of solutions containing different amounts of sodium hydroxide were prepared in volumetric flasks (10 ml) so as to get pH of the final solution between 6.0 and 14.0. Ionic strength was kept at 0.1 using KCl (1.0 M) solution. To this, 1.0 ml freshly prepared ethanolic solution of hydroxytriazene (1.0×10^{-4} M) was added. The solution was diluted to the mark with ethanol and absorbance was measured at 350 nm in each case. From these results, pK values were determined as per the reported methods and are given in Table 1. For comparison sake the reported pK values of parent compounds of different hydroxytriazene series have also been incorporated in the Table.

TABLE 1—pK VALUES OF HYDROXYTRIAZENES

Sl. no.	Hydroxytriazene	pK
1.	3-Hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene*	11.41
2.	3-Hydroxy-3-methyl-1-phenyltriazene**	12.11
3.	3-Hydroxy-3-ethyl-1-phenyltriazene**	12.28
4.	3-Hydroxy-3-n-propyl-1-phenyltriazene**	12.39
5.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-phenyltriazene	10.48
6.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-tolyltriazene	10.59
7.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-chloro-phenyltriazene	10.21
8.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-bromo-phenyltriazene	10.30
9.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-carboxy-phenyltriazene	10.34
10.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-methoxy-phenyltriazene	10.50
11.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-m-acetyl-phenyltriazene	10.49

* Refs. 1 and 2. ** Ref. 3.

Hydroxytriazenes have been assigned* an intramolecular hydrogen bonded structure and any substituent which has a tendency to weaken the hydrogen bonding will increase its acid character. Thus, the dissociation will depend upon the nature and position of the group present in benzene ring. A perusal of the result given in Table 1 reveals that 3-alkyl substituted hydroxytriazenes have high pK values than the pK value of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene. This may be attributed to +I effect of alkyl group which increases in the order methyl < ethyl < propyl. However, pK value of 3-hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-phenyltriazene is much less. This deviation may be due to steric effect of isopropyl group. The bulky isopropyl group attached

to the 3-nitrogen atom, perhaps, sterically inhibits the formation of intramolecular hydrogen bonded structure, thus reduces its stability and thereby increases the dissociation of proton resulting into lowering in pK value.

The compound 6 has pK value higher than the parent compound 5. This is attributed to +I effect of methyl group at *para* position. The compounds 7 and 8 have pK values lower than the parent compound 5. This is due to -I effect of halogens and it seems that +M effect of halogens is not operative due to strong +M effect of -N=N- group. The decrease in pK values of halogen substituted compounds is as per the decreasing inductive effect of halogens (F > Cl > Br > I). Decrease in pK value of compound 9 may be attributed to -M effect of -COOH group. The pK values of compounds 10 and 11 are comparable to that of the parent compound and as such difficult to explain.

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Effect of Conductance on Mobility of Ions by Paper-electrophoretic Studies

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A large number of separations of inorganic ions by electromigration in paper have been reported¹. But the physical studies on the electromigration of ions in paper were made by only few workers. Effects of valency of ions, pH, temperature, and electroosmotic effect on migrant were studied by various workers²⁻⁷. These studies promoted us to study the effect of conductance on the electrophoretic migration of ion. The present work reports the effect of conductance of migrant and conductance of carrier electrolyte on the electrophoretic migration of cations in the paper. As the mobility of a

cation can be derived from the distance traversed by the cation after necessary corrections, so attempt has been made to show the effect of conductance on the mobility of ions from the distance traversed by different migrants when electrophorised.

Experimental

A.R. quality of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were used. $\text{Pr}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ was prepared by dissolving Pr_2O_3 in nitric

TABLE 1—DISTANCE TRAVERSED BY MIGRANTS AGAINST VARYING CONDUCTANCES OF MIGRANTS

Migrant	Concentration of migrant <i>M</i>	Observed conductance of migrant $\mu \Omega^{-1}$	Molar conductance of migrant $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$	Distance of migration of migrants from the point of application (middle point of the band) cm		Carrier electrolyte (KNO_3) concentration <i>M</i>
CuSO_4	0.5	4.8×10^4	62.784	4.25		0.1
	0.25	2.8×10^4	73.248	5.05		
	0.166	2.1×10^4	82.734	5.15		
	0.125	1.8×10^4	94.176	5.25		
	0.1	1.5×10^4	98.1	5.35		
	0.066	1.3×10^4	128.81	5.4		
	0.05	1.0×10^4	130.8	5.5		
	0.033	0.8×10^4	158.45	5.6		
	0.025	0.6×10^4	183.12	5.7		
$\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	0.5	1.1×10^5	143.88	1.5		0.1
	0.25	5.6×10^4	146.49	2.7		
	0.166	5.2×10^4	165.46	2.8		
	0.125	3.3×10^4	172.65	2.9		
	0.1	2.8×10^4	183.12	3.05		
	0.066	2.2×10^4	218.0	3.15		
	0.05	1.8×10^4	235.44	4.0		
	0.033	1.3×10^4	257.63	4.8		
	0.025	1.1×10^4	287.76	4.85		
$\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	0.5	1.1×10^5	143.88	2.4		0.1
	0.25	5.65×10^4	147.80	2.7		
	0.166	4.1×10^4	161.53	3.2		
	0.125	3.3×10^4	172.65	4.2		
	0.1	2.9×10^4	189.66	4.3		
	0.066	2.0×10^4	198.18	4.4		
	0.05	1.7×10^4	222.36	4.7		
	0.033	1.1×10^4	242.1	4.8		
	0.025	1.0×10^4	261.6	4.9		
$\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	0.5	9.1×10^4	119.028	3.4		0.1
	0.25	5.3×10^4	138.648	4.1		
	0.166	5.15×10^4	163.5	4.6		
	0.125	3.2×10^4	167.424	4.7		
	0.1	2.7×10^4	176.58	4.8		
	0.066	2.0×10^4	198.181	5.0		
	0.05	1.6×10^4	209.28	5.2		
	0.033	1.1×10^4	218.0	5.4		
	0.025	0.9×10^4	235.44	5.8		
$\text{Pr}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	0.5	1.3×10^5	170.04	5.0		0.1
	0.25	7.1×10^4	185.736	5.2		
	0.166	5.2×10^4	204.86	5.3		
	0.125	5.1×10^4	214.51	5.5		
	0.1	3.3×10^4	215.82	5.7		
	0.066	2.5×10^4	247.72	5.8		
	0.05	2.2×10^4	287.76	4.2		
	0.033	1.6×10^4	317.09	4.1		
	0.025	1.3×10^4	340.08	3.9		

TABLE 2—DISTANCE TRAVERSED BY MIGRANTS AGAINST VARYING CONDUCTANCES OF CARRIER ELECTROLYTE

Carrier electrolyte	Concentration of carrier electrolyte <i>M</i>	Observed conductance of carrier electrolyte in $\mu \Omega^{-1}$	Molar conductance of carrier electrolyte in $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$	Distance of migration of migrants from the point of application (middle point of the band), cm				
				CuII	CoII	NiII	CdII	PrIII
KNO_3	0.2	3.4×10^4	111.18	2.1	3.1	2.6	1.9	1.8
	0.133	2.7×10^4	132.76	4.3	4.6	4.0	3.6	3.7
	0.1	2.2×10^4	143.88	5.2	5.3	4.7	4.5	4.8
	0.066	1.6×10^4	158.54	5.7	6.0	5.8	4.9	5.5

acid. Different concentrations of Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pr^{III} solutions were prepared by proper dilution from 1M solution. KNO_3 (0.2, 0.133, 0.1, 0.066 M) solutions were used as carrier electrolytes.

Conductance of different concentrations of solutions of migrants and carrier electrolyte were measured at 31° in Systronics 302 conductivity meter. Distance of migration of different-concentration solutions Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pr^{III} were recorded after electrophorising in Whatman Paper No. 1 using 1 drop (containing 10^{-4} g) of each solution in a Wieland and Fischer type⁸ horizontal electrophoretic apparatus for 1 h at 220 V using carrier electrolytes (i) 0.1M KNO_3 and (ii) varying the concentration (0.2, 0.133, 0.1, 0.66 M) of KNO_3 .

Results and Discussion

It is observed from Tables 1 and 2 that for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} ions, with increasing molar conductances of the migrant, the distance traversed increases, i.e. the mobility increases as expected, and with increasing molar conductances of the carrier electrolyte the mobility of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pr^{III} also increases. When the molar conductances of carrier electrolyte (KNO_3) are 148.88 and $158.54 \mu\Omega^{-1}$ at 31° the salt is about 80-90% dissociated, so the mobility of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pr^{III} are very high, when the molar conductance of KNO_3 is $111.18 \mu\Omega^{-1}$ at 31°, the movement of the ions being greatly retarded by electrical attraction owing to the close proximity of ion at such lower value of molar conductance of carrier electrolyte. Fig. 1 clearly indicates that there is a

Fig. 1.

sharp increase in the mobility of Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pr^{III} when the molar conductance of carrier electrolyte (KNO_3) increases from 111.18 to $148.8 \mu\Omega^{-1}$. However, in case of Pr^{III} with increasing molar conductance of the migrant its mobility at first increases and then decreases. Such sharp decrease in mobility of Pr^{III} at higher values of molar conductance of the migrant is probably due to hydrolysis, as all trivalent lanthanide ions are hydrolysed with dilution according to the equation⁹,

It is observed from Table 2 that upto 0.66 M concentration of the carrier electrolyte there is no possibility of hydrolysis of the migrants. It may be that if the concentration of carrier electrolyte is further decreased there is a possibility of hydrolysis of the migrants. But the experiment could not be performed because of the fact that the migrant cannot be developed due to high dilution of the carrier electrolyte.

It appears that by noting the conductance values of carrier electrolyte the degree of separation can be ascertained, since degree of separation depends on the degree of dissociation of electrolytes. Moreover, it is observed that with change in conductance the character of the species alters and also the mobility changes, so the possibility of separation becomes better. It can be concluded that by paper-electrophoretic studies the mobility of cations are indirectly proportional to the molar conductances of the salt of the corresponding cations and also to the molar conductances of the carrier electrolyte.

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Synthesis of Some Spiro[5.5]undecanes as Possible Analgesic Agents

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LEDNICER *et al.*¹ reported narcotic-like analgesic activity in 4-phenyl-4-(dimethylamino)cyclohexanone. Further investigation revealed that some 4-aryl-4-dialkylaminocyclohexanone ketals